

Yield components of three rice varieties transplanted at different seedling ages. Allahabad Agricultural Institute, India.

Seedling age (days)	Effective tillers (no./hill) ^a			Grains (panicle/no.)			1,000-grain wt (g)			Yield (t/ha)		
	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna	Bala	Saket 1	Ratna
24	12.5	9.7	13.7	122	140	119	18.5	19.8	19.4	2.6	3.2	3.1
29	10.2	11.1	13.8	116	152	124	18.5	19.7	19.5	2.6	3.6	3.8
34	9.9	10.4	13.1	111	135	118	17.9	19.6	19.1	2.4	3.0	2.9
39	8.6	9.7	12.3	100	132	114	17.7	19.3	19.1	1.3	2.9	2.8
44	7.3	9.5	10.4	93	132	107	17.3	19.2	18.8	1.0	2.1	2.0
49	5.2	7.4	8.7	89	123	105	17.3	18.2	18.3	1.0	1.6	1.0

^aTwo seedlings planted per hill at 20 × 20 cm.

while the medium- and long-duration varieties may be transplanted until 39 days for profitable rice production.

The experiment is being repeated in 1977 to better quantify the growth and yield performance of short-, medium-,

and long-duration rice varieties under Indian conditions. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Grain quality

The mechanism of gibberellic-acid action on rice

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Treating rice with gibberellic acid (GA) produces long and thin stems and causes lodging. Silica content in the cell walls of stems of treated plants is equal to that of control plants. GA inhibits tillering and activates ramification. Spikelet sterility becomes high and panicle weight becomes low.

GA reduces the content of riboflavin and free thiamine in leaves, but increases the content of total thiamine and cocarboxylase. It competitively inhibits flavin oxydases and increases indoleacetic acid (IAA) content. In the apexes of plants treated with GA, the ratio of RNA to DNA increases but the total protein content does not. The number of electrophoretical fractions of acid albumins decreases.

GA increases the variability of free amino acids set, but reduces their total content in primordial panicles of rice.

The content of free proline is reduced rather sharply, while that of histones is increased. The stream of information from nucleus to cytoplasm grows narrow with GA. GA is likely to affect the information transfer system.

Hence, this is the mechanism of GA action: proline (initiator of flowering) content is reduced, but the content of both histones (repressors of the generative group of genes) and growth stimulators (IAA) is increased. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

New sources of resistance to bacterial leaf streak of rice

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Bacterial leaf streak of rice, caused by *Xanthomonas translucens*, f. sp. *oryzicola*, is becoming a more important disease with intensive cultivation of newly introduced high yielding varieties. Both the early- and late-duration rices have been observed to become susceptible under conditions of high humidity, cloudiness, and drizzles. Thus the disease can become severe in high-rainfall areas of eastern and northeastern India. At the Central Rice Research Institute (CRR I), a severe incidence of the disease appeared on the variety Pankaj during kharif 1972. Several fixed cultivars of upland rice

grown during kharif 1977 were also severely affected.

Out of 50 artificially inoculated cultivars from the Assam Rice Collections, ARC 13899 and ARC 13962 were found resistant. Among the popular varieties tested, NC 1281 was highly resistant. It is being extensively used at CRR I to develop high yielding varieties that are sensitive to photoperiod. It has good tolerance to gall midge and is considered to have high photosynthetic ability under low light intensity. Several F₄ progeny from the cross NC 1281/ Pankaj were artificially inoculated during kharif 1977. The progeny clearly segregated for susceptibility or resistance to bacterial leaf streak. That shows that the inheritance may be simple and it may not be difficult to fix resistant lines.